

GAMIFICATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689661>

ELSEVIER

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Abstract: The article discusses the use of gamification as an effective tool for optimizing the educational process when organizing training using various elements of gamification that makes the learning process more motivated and "closer" to the modern generation, accustomed to the daily use of the digital environment, computer, and mobile resources.

Keywords: digital environment, an effective tool active, communication, gamification, motivate.

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Received: 22-02-2023

Accepted: 22-02-2023

Published: 22-02-2023

Introduction:

The positive role of educational games has been known for a very long time, many teachers successfully use role-playing games and other game methods for educational purposes. The terms "gamification" and appeared with the spread of information technology and were associated with the introduction of gaming techniques in various processes: personnel management, promotion of goods and services, business processes, training [20,272].

Gamification in the field of education is developing quite rapidly due to the development of digital technologies, distance learning and the involvement of the "generation of computer games" in the educational environment. Gamification is the application of gaming techniques and elements in originally non-gaming processes. The game helps to create a stable feedback with students, to direct and correct the actions of participants, to intensify the assimilation of educational material. The main advantage of gamification is to increase motivation for learning through involvement in the game process. Thus, high motivation helps to cope with difficult situations, show perseverance and purposefulness, and look for effective problem-solving strategies.

Discussions:

Often, traditional teaching methods focus on learner errors. The student is shown what he did wrong. In game methods, the emphasis is on the content and principles of achieving success. Learners are not afraid to "learn from their mistakes" [25, 45]. Gamification allows the teacher gradually complicate learning tasks, as in a computer game from simple to complex levels. Controlling the

process of the game, the teacher receives feedback from students active communication takes place. With the help of gamification, it is possible to overcome some of the problems and contradictions that exist in teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic educational organizations: "insufficient motivation of students; initial multi-level training of students.

Game method

The basis of the business game is the process of imitation that takes place during the business game. The main task of the business game is to teach socio-cultural norms and rules for conducting a conversation (discussion) in a foreign language especially in English, business behavior and business image. If we proceed from the assumption that it is necessary to prepare for the game and sum up the results, then the game can have the following structure [15,167].

In the preparation phase, students get acquainted with the initial situation of the game, discuss the content aspects, the main problem of the game, as well as the interests of the players. In addition to meaningful preparation, students should familiarize themselves with the formal framework of the game, with its construction (beginning of the game, completion, summing up).

At this stage, there is a distribution of roles. Since the first game phase is needed, as a rule, primarily to get acquainted with the game, then usually after the introduction of the first phase, an in-depth introduction to the business game is carried out, clarification of issues that have arisen when working with the game model or are important for further implementation.

The reflection phase (summing up) can have different accents depending on the course of the game. As a rule, initially the main emphasis is on discussing the course and results of the game.

In this phase, we can analyze both the causes and consequences of the behavior of the players in the decision-making process, as well as develop strategies for behavior in the subsequent phase of the game. In addition, it is usually appropriate and desirable to critically evaluate and sometimes modify the game model [17, 27]. Based on the results of a scientific study, we will try to generalize the qualification features of the business game in relation not only to the financial and economic specialty, but also to the specialty of students in the oil and gas industry. The main features include:

Game roles are set by the situation itself, while the functional (real) and game (artificial) role goals of the participants are clearly distinguished; Participants in the game actively interact with each other as required by the presented socio-economic conditions and prescribed roles [2,174];

The group has a common goal of activity and each participant has his own individual role; the decision-making process is individual-group, when participants

first make decisions in accordance with their individual role goals, and then agree on them, since the final implementation of individual decisions depends on the nature of the general decision made [7,130];

The situation provides an opportunity to consider alternative solutions;

The fundamental difference between a business game and all other simulation games is that during the game, the participants implement a chain of management decisions that directly affect the control object;

Participants' actions are evaluated both in terms of final and intermediate results.

In foreign language teaching, the problem of using business games in foreign language classes also attracts the attention of scientists involved in economics, oil and gas, technology and other education, where cooperation is carried out. For example, the classification of business games proposed by Heinz Clippert in his concept of a business game is well known. The author came to the conclusion that simple interactive games, based primarily on argumentation and purposeful negotiations, are quite suitable for encouraging students to actively and multilaterally consider the problems of decision-making in their specialty. Clippert defines interactive games as multi-phase negotiating games, single-phase conference games, discussions like pros and cons [2, 176].

The comprehension of the functions of business games made it possible to single out the following of them: culturally oriented business games may consist in creating educational and communicative prerequisites for:

- Mastering the technique of speech and business behavior in situations of intercultural communication;
- Teaching the basics of debatable interpersonal (intercultural) communication;
- Development of integrative creative skills to communicate based on interdisciplinary knowledge;
- The developing function involves the development of students' intellectual abilities, creative imagination, communication skills, learning skills in a social context (teamwork, mutual assistance, responsibility);
- cultural studies function includes enrichment of socio-cultural and cultural horizons of students, development of skills to perceive and understand the specific features of the traditions of behavior, manners of communication, mentality of representatives of another culture, education of tolerance, friendliness towards communication partners [14, 269].

All these functions are interconnected, complement each other and have a direct impact on the development of the personality of the future specialist. As practice shows, students actively and willingly perceive their roles, because the

game opens up the prospect for them to experience social forms of behavior and approach the reality of game situations, without being afraid to express their point of view.

The game contributes to the actualization of language skills and speech skills of students, immerses in the socio-cultural environment of the country of the language being studied and encourages constructive thinking, the search for a solution to the conflict situation. This, in turn, requires going beyond the topic and searching for additional information based on interdisciplinary connections.

Conclusion:

Gamification is a promising direction in teaching foreign languages in higher education. Conducting educational games, competitions, quizzes, gamification of mastering speech skills and control of the studied material can be an effective way to intensify learning processes. Involvement in group work and increasing the motivation of students contributes to the development of communicative competence and improvement of the quality of the educational process.

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